

The Influence of Motivation, Empowerment, on Organizational Commitment: Role of LMX as a Mediator

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Abstract: *The objective of this paper is to determine the relationship between motivated, empowerment and organizational commitment, through existing LMX as mediating among employees in Jordanian municipalities. The findings show that there is a positive association between antecedent behavioral and organizational commitment. In conclusion, municipalities should consider in enhancing motivated, empowerment and organizational culture to boost the level of their employees' commitment.*

Keywords: *Motivation, Empowerment, Organizational Commitment, LMX, municipalities*

1. INTRODUCTION

The most valuable asset in an organization is its employees. (Kim, Kang, et al. 2016) argues that the success of an organization depends on employees' commitment and participation. In addition, Anitha and Begum (2016) argue that a high commitment environment improves employee retention rate, reduce operating costs and promotes employees' performance and efficiency. According to Yokel, Allen et al. (1994) organizational commitment is a psychological state that characterizes the employees' relationships with the organization. It is said that strong organizational commitment causes employees to work harder to achieve the objectives of the organization (Meyer and Allen 2004).

Within the scope of the present work, the local government sector was chosen, given its relevance in the country's economy. The case study has provided information inputs on the real world, from which concepts and propositions were formed, and a theory generation was attempted. The enlargement of urban areas which correlate significantly with the nation's economic growth entails an increase in the problems, needs, and complexities relating to urban governance. Thus, local government is undergoing tremendous pressure to carry through effective management due to increase in urbanization, education levels of the population and the industrialization of the nation (Hashim and dan Perakaunan 2016). Reforming the local government and transforming its valuable human capital to serve the public better are efforts precondition to providing excellent and high-quality service to the stakeholders and its clients in the 21st century. Municipal service delivery is a challenge facing many municipalities in Jordan; It is, therefore, essential to understanding how to improve municipal service delivery, to determine what interventions are necessary, and to understand the underlying issues behind the problem. The initial goal of the study is the examination of the level impact of motivation, empowerment towards the organizational commitment in the first category Municipalities in Jordan with LMX as mediator.

2. Literature Review

The definitions associated with organizational commitment, commonly relate the behavior to the attitude of the employee (Potipiroon and Ford 2017). Literature by Blau and Boal (1987); Mathieu and Zajac (1990) reaffirms organizational commitment as being the personal attachment between the employees, and the goals of the institutions they are acquainted with. Meyer and Herscovitch (2001) further describe the traits of committed employees as the ones willing to stay with the institution in times of need, and express their commitment by attending work regularly, working a full day and willing to do extra, looks after company assets, and feels being a part of the vision and mission of the institution. Employee's work-related behavior in an organization is commonly caused or affected by the commitment given by the employees to the organization; Lecturers engage in positive behaviors such as high work performance when they are experiencing high organizational commitment (Naidu and Chand 2014).

2.1. The relationship between LMX and Organizational commitment

The association between LMX and commitment has become the foundation of a new era of managing diversified workforce as claimed by Yahaya and Ebrahim (2016). The quality of leader-member

exchanges has been found to correlate with OC positively. When subordinates in high LMX relationships are given more responsibility, support, and influence they will often display greater loyalty to the organization. Yukl (1989) found that high-quality LMX relationships resulted in employees being more committed to both task completion as well as assisting the leader in meeting goals. Personal characteristics shown to relate to OC include the length of stay in the organization and age. Conclusions on these personal characteristics derive from Becker's (1960) "side bet" theory, stating that the more an individual invests in an organization (i.e., time, money, and values), and the greater loss for that employee when quitting.

Meyer and Allen (1997) found that employees' affective organizational commitment relates to the quality of the working relationship with their manager. Kurtessis, Eisenberger et al. (2017) indicated that supervisory support and perceived leadership ability related positively to affective organizational commitment. It is therefore expected that the leadership behaviors of the supervisor will be positively related to the level of affective organizational commitment of subordinates.

2.2. The relationship between motivation and organizational commitment.

Motivation is concerned with the factors that influence people to behave in certain ways (Armstrong 2016). It includes factors that cause, channel, and sustain human behavior in a particular committed direction. For the purpose of this study, it is defined as a means by which organization solicit the efforts of its employees for the job done so as to attain the organizational goals. Motivation can either be intrinsic and extrinsic, depend on the type of employees, nature of the job and the working environment. In other means words, motivation is a means to reduce the gap which exists between the individual's actual state and some desired state. Motivation and commitment are closely related concepts (van der Voet, Steijn, et al. 2017). The higher the employee's motivation, the more they are committed to their jobs (Laschinger, Read, et al. 2016). Motivation and commitment theory that both developed in an attempt to understand, predict, and influence employee behavior. As we noted at the outset, however, motivation theorists have generally been more concerned with explaining task performance. This is clearly reflected in Locke's (1997) model. In contrast, commitment theorists have historically focused more on explaining employee retention or turnover. The latter has clearly changed, however, as is evident in Meyer and Herscovitch's (2001) model where predictions are made concerning the effects of commitment on any behavior (focal or discretionary) of relevance to the target of that commitment. Therefore, in light of the obvious overlap in purpose and implication, we argue that integration of commitment and motivation theory is both plausible and warranted (Meyer et al., 1993). In this study will be discussed the motivation by sub-dimensions: appreciation, facilities, promotion& growth, reward.

2.3. The relationship between empowerment and organizational commitment.

Empowerment, Commitment, Empowered followers are more likely to have greater latitude to make decisions as well as feel given more responsibility, which in turn improves their level of commitment to their organizations (Thomas and Velthouse 1990). Psychologically empowered individuals tend to believe that they are making a difference in meaningful ways, which results in performance for the sake of their organization and at higher levels of organizational commitment (Han, Seo, et al. 2016). Han, Seo et al. (2016) found the direct and indirect impacts of transformational leadership on organizational commitment through psychological empowerment. Khanjari (2017) found effect empowerment on commitment. In addition, the extent to which empowerment reaches managers and non-managerial staff will vary among organizations. It will depend partly on the readiness of top-line managers to "let go" control and formwork partnerships with their subordinates, and partly on the training the staff has received to develop the skills needed for accepting new responsibilities, (Cunningham et al., 1996).

3. Leader-member exchange (LMX).

research on LMX suggests that members in higher quality dyads are more committed to the organization than are members in lower quality dyads Basu and Green (1997); Yukl (1989); Duchon, Green et al. (1986); Dansereau, Graen et al. (1975). With regard to the relationship between LMX quality and OC, several studies have provided evidence that organizational and supervisory support plays a critical role in enhancing OC Allen and Meyer, (1990); Eisenberger, Hornedo et al. (1986). The recent study by Joo et al. (2012) supported the results of the previous studies that a relational context is an important factor for OC.

While a number of contemporary leadership theories examine the effects of leader behaviors on outcomes for the employees or teams which they supervise, LMX theory was developed as a means of understanding outcomes at the member, team, and organizational levels by examining the leader-member

dyadic relationship. In a recent review by Riggs (2016), the author tells us: “According to the LMX approach, leaders are closer, friendlier, more inclusive, and more communicative with some members who report to them. In other words, leaders form a high-quality trust, affect, and respect-based relationships with a subset of their team, while with other members they tend to have a lower-quality exchange that is limited to the employee and the leader’s job description.

3.1. The relationship between motivation and LMX.

How do leaders who foster positive social exchanges with their follower's effect on motivation? In addition to the direct effects of motivation on LMX. Because LMX is a dyadic relationship between the leader and the member, certain information is conveyed through the development and maintenance of this relationship. For that reason, it is possible that through this relationship, information about the importance and usefulness of motivation is conveyed (Qu, Janssen, et al. 2017). If this is the case, then, a positive relationship with the leader could influence a person’s motivation and would impact on their commitment. Furthermore, high-quality leader-member relationships have a positive influence on employees’ levels of empowerment, which are described by Neubert, Hunter et al. (2016) as a motivating factor (or ‘empowerment as motivation), and supported empirically in other studies (Liden, Wayne, et al. 2000).

3.2. The relationship between empowerment and LMX.

Additionally, The extant literature has established that LMX quality (Gerstner and Day 1997) and empowerment (Seibert, Silver, et al. 2004) are both positively associated with desired outcomes. However, little is known about how these variables interact. In particular, does the absence or presence of empowerment on the job make the relationships between LMX and job outcomes stronger or weaker? Suggested that the established relationships between LMX and the consequences of, turnover intentions, job performance, are strongest when empowerment is lowest, as employees are not motivated by the jobs ((Harris, Wheeler, et al. 2009). Thus, this study may help to specify the situations when LMX has either a greater or lesser impact on empowerment. The LMX and empowerment researches stream is important as previous researchers have called for examinations of the interactions of these variables and how they affect organizational consequences. It is expected that find the most positive outcomes when both LMX and empowerment are high, and the most negative outcomes when both were low. However, is expected LMX relationship quality will be differentially important depending on how empowered an individual feels (Llewellyn, 2008).

4. Theoretical framework

5. Discussion and Conclusion

In this paper, described factors included motivation, empowerment, and organizational commitment, through existing LMX as mediating variable. The theoretical propositions presented in this study supplement

our understanding as to how to increase organizational commitment. Focusing on Jordanian municipalities need does not jeopardize organizational goals; rather, it leads to employees who have increased levels of commitment to the organization and its goals, which is consistent with preliminary studies positively associating anticipate behavior with organizational commitment. Specifically, previous studies showed that motivation, empowerment, positively impacts organizational commitment, and empirical studies found the LMX effect in this sector (Ibrahim 2014) because employees develop arranging to leaders and reciprocate with a willingness to extend themselves on behalf of the organization (Schaubroeck, Shen, et al. 2017). Furthermore, the approach organizational commitment take in relationships with subordinates, along with respect, and genuine behaviors exhibited to develop their followers' autonomy and responsibility increases employees commitment to engage in the municipalities (Yahaya and Ebrahim 2016).

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